

EVALUATING THE DIAGNOSTIC PRECISION: INTRAOPERATIVE FROZEN SECTION COMPARED WITH PERMANENT HISTOPATHOLOGY IN PATIENTS OF HEAD AND NECK TUMORS

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Abstract

Objective: To determine the diagnostic accuracy of frozen section for diagnosis of head and neck tumor taking histopathology as gold standard.

Study design: Cross sectional study

Place and duration of the study: It is a prospective study held in University of Lahore Teaching Hospital, Lahore, Pakistan from December 2024 to June 2025.

Methodology: Sample size of 125 cases was were enrolled who presented with tumors in head and neck region and underwent biopsy for confirmation of type of tumor that needs intraoperative frozen section for complete resection were enrolled from the surgical wards. Frozen section results will be compared to permanent histopathology. Collected data will be statistically analyzed using SPSS software version 24. 2x2 table was built to calculate the sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV and diagnostic performance of frozen section.

Results: In this study, we included frozen sections of total 125 patients with mean age of 53.25 ± 12.85 years. There were more males 87 (69.6%) than females 38 (30.4%). There were 75 (60%) patients who had history of smoking, 81 (64.8%) had history of tobacco chewing, while 31 (24.8%) took dental treatment before. Among all, tumor of buccal mucosa 43 (34.4%) is more common than other sites, including mandible 38 (30.4%), neck 25 (20%), maxilla 12 (9.6%) and tongue 7 (5.6%). It has been observed that among all the cases, frozen section showed 100% Sensitivity and 100% specificity, as all the predicted cases were confirmed on histopathology. The PPV and NPV of frozen section was also 100%. Thus, the overall diagnostic accuracy of frozen section was 100%.

Conclusion: Thus, frozen section is a reliable method for differentiation of malignant and benign head and neck tumors.

INTRODUCTION

Head and neck squamous cell carcinoma (HNSCC), the seventh most common cancer diagnosis worldwide, is a group of malignancies that affect the oral cavity, pharynx, hypopharynx, larynx, nasal cavity, and salivary glands. GLOBOCAN estimates that head and neck cancer accounts for around 4.5% of all cancer diagnoses and deaths annually, with 450,000 fatalities and 890,000 new cases.^{1, 2} The disease's incidence seems to be rising, and considering the drop in smoking, especially in wealthy nations, several etiological alterations have been suggested.^{3, 4} An correct diagnosis is the real foundation upon which logical therapy should be based. Diagnosis is the art of identifying the nature of a disease. There are many diagnostic types used in the head and neck tumor care workflow.^{5, 6}

Most frequently used in oncological surgery, the frozen section is a pathological method that uses microscopic study of tissue to give a quick diagnosis.⁷ In order to determine the extent of illness and confirm the diagnosis of previously biopsied pathologic processes, as well as to diagnose newly detected lesions intraoperatively, frozen section examination has become routine procedure.⁸ To determine the margin status for excision of head and neck primary carcinomas and to further avoid local recurrence, frozen sections are frequently used.^{8, 9}

The procedure and results of intraoperative frozen section analysis should be carefully examined as one component of the overall therapy concept, given that patient survival has not increased despite advancements in operative and adjuvant therapeutic protocols. We looked at whether IFSA offers diagnostic accuracy and reliability to establish the limit of invasive growth of carcinoma for appropriate resection and, consequently, the prognosis of patients. Intraoperative frozen section analysis is contrasted with the patients' survival rate, illness recurrence, and ultimate resection status.

METHODOLOGY:

After approval from institutional review board (IRB letter number: UCD/ERCA/24/1567,

dated: 10/12/2024), this cross sectional study was held in University of Lahore Teaching Hospital, Lahore, Pakistan from December 2024 to June 2025. Sample size of 125 cases was estimated with 95% confidence level, 3% absolute precision required and percentage of accuracy of frozen section i.e. 97%.¹⁰ All the patients who fulfilled following criteria were enrolled by using non-probability, consecutive sampling technique.

Inclusion criteria: Patient age less than 60 years of either gender presented with tumors in head and neck region and underwent biopsy for confirmation of type of tumor that needs intraoperative frozen section for complete resection were enrolled from the surgical wards.

Exclusion criteria: Patients with extracapsular spread of tumor, extensive necrosis, metastasized into lungs or malignant melanoma (melanocytic lesion contraindicated to frozen section) were excluded from the sample.

We evaluate the intraoperative frozen section compared to definite postoperative histopathological resection status and see the post operative local reoccurrence during 1 year time period. Microscopic analysis of tissue in order to make a rapid diagnosis. Tumor free border of atleast 10mm to reduce the risk of positive margin due to mucosal shrinkage. Tumor margin along with at least one specimen at depth of tumor bed. Frozen section results will be compared to permanent histopathology. Collected data will be statistically analyzed using SPSS software version 24. 2x2 table was built to calculate the sensitivity, specificity, positive and negative predictive values and overall diagnostic performance of frozen section for confirmation of head and neck malignant tumors.

RESULTS

In this study, we included frozen sections of total 125 patients with mean age of 53.25 ± 12.85 years. There were more males 87 (69.6%) than females 38 (30.4%). Mostly patients were presented from urban areas 82 (65.6%). Among all, there were few students 6 (4.8%), who presented with head and neck tumors. There

were 75 (60%) patients who had history of smoking, 81 (64.8%) had history of tobacco chewing, 14 (11.2%) were also gutka chewers, while 31 (24.8%) took dental treatment before,

7 (5.6%) had diabetes and 20 (16%) had hypertension. NO patient had family history of cancer. Table-I

Table-I: Basic demographic details of participants (n = 125)

	n (%)
Age (years)	53.25 ± 12.85
Gender	
Males	87 (69.6%)
Females	38 (30.4%)
Residence	
Rural	43 (34.4%)
Urban	82 (65.6%)
Occupation	
Job	49 (39.2%)
Business	26 (20.8%)
Housewife	38 (30.4%)
Farmer	6 (4.8%)
Student	6 (4.8%)
History of	
Smoking	75 (60%)
Tobacco Chewing	81 (64.8%)
Gutka chewing	14 (11.2%)
Taken dental treatment	31 (24.8%)
Diabetes	7 (5.6%)
Hypertension	20 (16%)
Family history of cancer	Nil

Among all, tumor of buccal mucosa 43 (34.4%) is more common than other sites, including mandible 38 (30.4%), neck 25 (20%), maxilla 12 (9.6%) and tongue 7 (5.6%). More than half of patients had TNM staging T4, nodular

involvement was involved in more than 50% cases i.e. N1: 12 (9.6%), N2: 44 (35.2%) and N3: 12 (9.6%). No metastatic disease observed in the whole sample. Table-II

Table-II: Details of tumor (n = 125)

	n (%)
Maxilla	12 (9.6%)
Mandible	38 (30.4%)
Buccal mucosa	43 (34.4%)
Neck	25 (20%)
Tongue	7 (5.6%)
TNM staging	
Tumor stage 1	6 (4.8%)
Tumor stage 2	7 (5.6%)
Tumor stage 3	31 (24.8%)
Tumor stage 4	81 (64.8%)
Nodular involvement	
N0	57 (45.6%)
N1	12 (9.6%)

N2	44 (35.2%)
N3	12 (9.6%)
Metastasis	
M0	125 (100%)

It has been observed that among all the cases, frozen section showed 100% Sensitivity and 100% specificity, as all the predicted cases were confirmed on histopathology. The PPV and

NPV of frozen section was also 100%. Thus, the frozen section exhibited the diagnostic performance of 100% in this study. The concordance rate was also 100%. Table-III

Table-III: Accuracy of the frozen section in diagnosing the head and neck malignant tumors in comparison to histopathology (n = 125)

		Histopathology		Total
		Positive	Negative	
Frozen section	Positive	6	0	6
	Negative	0	119	119
Total		6	119	125

Sensitivity=100%; specificity=100%; PPV=100%; NPV=100%; Diagnostic accuracy=100%

DISCUSSION

In this study, we included frozen sections of total 125 patients with mean age of 53.25 ± 12.85 years. Among both gender, males are more prone to head and neck tumor, due to smoking and pan / tobacco and gutka chewing. Among all, tumor of buccal mucosa 43 (34.4%) is more common than other sites, including mandible 38 (30.4%), neck 25 (20%), maxilla 12 (9.6%) and tongue 7 (5.6%). In our study, we observed that there were only 6 (4.8%) cases of malignant head and neck tumor, while 119 (95.2%) cases had benign tumor. Frozen section showed 100% sensitivity and 100% specificity, as all the predicted cases were confirmed on histopathology. Additionally, the frozen section's PPV and NPV were 100%. Consequently, the frozen section's total diagnostic accuracy was 100%.

One important method that pathologists employ during the intraoperative consultation is frozen section examination. It is a crucial part of a surgical theater complex and plays a significant role in the surgical therapy of patients with neoplastic illness. Dr. Louis B. Wilson created the contemporary frozen section technique in 1905. The cryostat's invention in 1960 made frozen sections an extremely precise intraoperative method of

determining margin status. Surgeons from a variety of professions frequently utilize it to quickly determine whether a tumor is present in tissues; the surgical margins being the most frequently used example.^{11, 12}

The therapeutic utility of entire-circumferential intra-operative frozen sections for the whole excision of tongue squamous cell carcinoma in 276 patients was assessed in a study by Asoda et al. They came to the conclusion that frozen sections are a useful method for obtaining 100% sensitivity and 100% NPV for the full resection of tumors with negative margins. Additionally, they found that frozen section increased diagnostic accuracy when combined with iodine staining.¹³ Another research by Wasif et al., on 94 individuals having oral squamous cell carcinoma indicated that the overall diagnostic accuracy was 99%, the sensitivity of frozen section was 50%, specificity was 99.8%, while the PPV and NPV were 75% and 99.3%, respectively. They came to the conclusion that frozen sections are an extremely helpful tool that can assist surgeons in determining whether or not sufficient clean surgical margins have been established during surgery.¹⁴

Nayanar et al., conducted a study on head and neck tumors and observed The diagnosis of malignant tumors using that frozen segment has a sensitivity of 82.05% and a specificity of 96.46%. For a satisfactory concordance rate,

they suggested a minimum of three to four sections, the ideal cryostat temperature, a reasonable section thickness, and high-quality staining.¹⁵ According to other research, the accuracy percentage of frozen portions of the head and neck is between 96% and 98%.^{16, 17} Adhikari et al., We out a research in India and found that 97% of frozen section diagnoses were accurate overall. 94% was the sensitivity, 87% was the specificity, 90% was the PPV, and 93% was the NPV. There was a 90.2% concordance rate and a 9.8% discordance rate.¹⁰ While in our study, the concordance rate was 100%.

In a research carried out in the United States, the frozen section's sensitivity and specificity were 76.9% and 67.9%, respectively, while its PPV and NPV were 27.8% and 94.8%.¹⁸ Ali et al., also conducted a similar research in Karachi and observed a higher rate of sensitivity and specificity of frozen section in head and neck tumors (88.81% and 94.84%, respectively).¹⁹

Regarding the handling of such specimens once they are received in the frozen section area, there is no agreement. The sensitivity for detecting tiny tumor foci is probably boosted by cutting many tissue sections, but there has to be a balance struck between the somewhat higher sensitivity and pragmatic considerations like expense and time. To the best of our knowledge, the majority of centers only cut two complete hematoxylin and eosin sections each margin specimen, with the pathologist having the option to make a third level cut.²⁰⁻²²

The significance of frozen sections in determining the surgical margin intraoperatively has been refuted by other earlier research.²³ There is conflicting data about the relationship between frozen sections and better overall prognoses; some researchers found no correlation at all between frozen sections and overall outcomes, while others discovered prognostic advantages.²⁴ A prior study that was comparable to ours discovered that intraoperative frozen section histology had a high sensitivity when compared to final specimen histology.²⁵

Algadi et al., observed that frozen section had sensitivity and specificity of 50% and 100%, while PPV and NPV of 100% and 97.8%, respectively. The overall diagnostic accuracy was

97.9% when evaluated for mucosal tumor margins in cases of oral squamous cell carcinoma.²³ They found frozen sections to be a reasonably helpful method for intraoperatively evaluating tumor margins, which is different from what we discovered. According to their proposal, toluidine blue is a more sensitive method, and screening margins with it prior to frozen section sample might increase the number of tumor margins that can be identified. A poor frozen section sensitivity of 45.4% in determining margin status was also revealed by another investigation by Mair et al.²⁶

CONCLUSION

Thus, frozen section is a reliable method for differentiation of malignant and benign head and neck tumors. In future, we can reply on findings of intra-operative frozen section for confirmation of malignant head and neck tumors.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST:

None.

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